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AI AND HUMANISTIC VALUES AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY OF UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR, CROSS RIVER STATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The world today seems to be driven by latest scientific innovations. It has been suggested by many observers that the rise of Artificial Intelligence will consequently lead to the takeover of most tasks hitherto done by humans by these machines. This will lead to redundancy among human beings, a feeling of frustration among many, insecurity and a possible extinction of the human species. Since the phenomenal appearance of AI in the late 1940s, humanity has had to grapple with some ethical humanistic concerns about the application of this

scientific innovation. At the core of this paper is the concern whether ethical values could be maintained by University students in this AI-driven era. In light of this value shifts therefore, this paper investigated the alignment and perception of AI vis-à-vis humanistic values among University students in Nigeria, with particular focus on the students of the University of Calabar, Cross River State. With a purposeful random sampling of three hundred (300) respondents, the study used survey research method, leaning on Technological Mediation Theory and Value Sensitive Design Theory as its theoretical lenses. A questionnaire was designed in order to seek the opinion of participants on the subject under investigation. The data collected were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize students' demographic characteristics and general trends. Inferential statistics was used to test the research hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that most students view AI as intellectually beneficial but are concerned about its moral, behavioural, and spiritual implications, with a significant 54.6% of participants agreeing that AI is a threat to the belief in the Supreme Being. The study concluded and recommended that critical stakeholders should integrate AI ethics modules into curriculum across departments, thereby, promoting reflective practices among students on how AI affects human interactions. This will encouraged interdisciplinary dialogue between technology and humanities faculties.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence, Humanistic Values, Human Dignity, University Students, Technological Mediation Theory, Value Sensitive Design, And Scientific Innovation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the early 1940s has birthed changes in almost all spheres of human activities including the education sector. The appreciation and application of AI among both teachers and students became more prominent and accepted during and post COVID-19 pandemic when teaching and knowledge was shared via AI tools more than ever before. The recent surge in the use of AI tools made the researchers to this paper to become agitated as to what would become of one's faith in the Supreme Being, and in humanistic values such as dignity, empathy, and morality. Four scenario's spurred research interest in this study. First, the regular and constant reference to some AI mobile apps such as Chat GPT, Meta AI, Gauth, AI games,

and AI chatbot by my daughter every evening after school kept me concerned about the number of hard copy textbooks I bought for her. Each time I ask her: "How about your Mathematics text or Physics text?" The response is almost always spontaneous! "Daddy, AI has it all and is quick!". Second, as a teacher in the University, we administered a test on the 3rd of January, 2025. This was a three hundred level class, and during the invigilation, five students were caught cheating. Three of the students had typed the test questions and requested the answers from their mobile smart phones, while the other two were caught writing out the answers from digital smart wrist watches. The answers found in all the five devices were not only correct, but articulately arranged in perfect order.

Figure

The third scenario was in a public transport vehicle where some students on vacation were travelling back home after their semester examinations. While on transit, I listened keenly to the conversation among them on the use of AI and how it has lessened the burden of sourcing for hard copy books during assignments. Fourth, in one of the Sunday Masses, the Priest asked how many people came to church with their Bibles? Almost everybody lifted up mobile devices and not Bibles. Having shared these experiences with other co-researchers, we became curious to investigate the humanistic values among university students, in light of the prevalence of AI applications, appreciation, and use among students in the University of Calabar, Cross River State of Nigeria.

As a result of the above observations and in view of the fact that AI and its use among university students and scholars have increased, it has become

pertinent that we find out its influences on student's value systems, how it connects humanistic education and technology adoption, and how this applies to a case study methodology focused on students' perceptions of its benefits and risks. The study therefore, presented the problem statement, two theoretical framework that best suit the case study, the review of related literature, materials, methodology of the analysis and discussion of key research findings, and finally, the summary, recommendation and conclusion based on the strengths of the recommended theories used in the study.

1.1. Statement Of the Problem

The rapid integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies into educational institutions worldwide has introduced new dynamics into the learning environment and the University of Calabar is no

exception. From AI – driven learning platforms to decision-making algorithms, students increasingly interact with systems that not only facilitate academic success but also influence their perception, behaviours, and value systems. While AI promises efficiency, personalization, and access to information and knowledge, concerns are emerging regarding its impact on essential humanistic values such as empathy, fairness, morality, autonomy, dignity, and critical thinking – values traditionally nurtured through human – centered education.

In the context of Nigerian Universities, and specifically the University of Calabar, the adoption of AI technologies remains relatively recent and under-examined. There is limited empirical evidence on how these technologies mediate students' ethical reasoning and social consciousness. More critically, there is a growing risk that an uncritical embrace of AI might inadvertently erode foundational humanistic values by promoting efficiency over empathy, algorithmic decision-making over human judgment, and data-driven interactions over meaningful human relationships and quick answer over morality. This potential conflict raises urgent concern: How does the daily use of AI technologies shape students' understanding and prioritization of humanistic values? This is the problem this study investigated.

1.2. Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to examine the impact of AI technologies on the humanistic values of undergraduate students at the University of Calabar.

Apart from the above broad objective, other specific objectives are to:

- i. Investigate how AI technologies mediate students' perceptions, actions, and experiences related to humanistic values such as empathy, fairness, morality, autonomy, justice, and dignity.
- ii. Assess the extent to which students at the University of Calabar are aware of the ethical implication associated with their use of AI technologies.
- iii. Explore students' attitudes and reflections regarding the influence of AI on their moral, ethical, and social development.
- iv. Analyze how AI will reduce examination malpractice among students.
- v. Examine the role of AI in inspiring academic transformation and the spirit of inquiry among students of the University of Calabar.
- vi. Assess how AI will create a compassionate

humane school environment and improve human relations.

- vii. Explore how AI application will improve human dignity, the right to work, and dispel fears of machines talking over human affairs.

1.3. Research Hypotheses

Since this study is quantitative research, here are some hypotheses for the research.

1.4. Null Hypotheses (H_0)

1. H_{01} : AI technologies do not significantly mediate students' perceptions and experiences regarding humanistic values at the University of Calabar.
2. H_{02} : Students at the University of Calabar are not significantly aware of the ethical implications of using AI technologies.
3. H_{03} : There is no significant relationship between students' use of AI systems and the preservation of humanistic values.
4. H_{04} : Students' attitudes toward AI use do not significantly reflect concerns for ethical, moral, or social development.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To adequately address the objectives of this research work, two theoretical frameworks have been applied because of the peculiar nature of the case study.

- a. **Technological Mediation Theory (TMT)**: Ihde (1990), Verbeek (2011), and Rosenberger and Verbeek (2015) argue that Technological Mediation Theory (TMT) is rooted in post phenomenology and that it examines how technologies shape human perceptions, actions, and values rather than being an unbiased tool. The implication is that technologies actively mediate the relationship between humans and the world, thereby influencing experiences, behaviours, and moral consideration of issues.

In the context of Artificial Intelligence, particularly among University of Calabar students, technological Mediation Theory asserts that AI systems or tools do not only serve students but transform how they perceive their academic environments, their perception of learning processes, and how they engage with humanistic values such as empathy, dignity, and justice. Thus, students' interactions with Artificial Intelligence may covertly influence their views of autonomy, sense of responsibility, and social relations and connections.

Applying the Technological Mediation Theory

within the context of the University of Calabar, it is pertinent to note that students' use of AI, for instance chatGPT, chatbots, recommendation algorithms, and other AI - assisted learning tools, could mediate their understanding and prioritization of humanistic values. Furthermore, TMT is apt as it makes provision for AI to explore and shape students' ethical reasoning. TMT also explores whether Artificial Intelligence strengthens or diminishes empathy and care among students globally and those of the University of Calabar in particular. TMT also explores how students elsewhere and those within the study area experience concepts such as fairness and agency when using Artificial Intelligence. Summarily, therefore, Technological Mediation Theory underpins the study's exploration of how the presence and use of AI technology modulate students' value systems in the University of Calabar.

b. Value Sensitive Design (VSD): Value Sensitive Design is the second theoretical framework used in this research study. VSD is an approach that has to do with technology development and evaluation that systematically incorporates human values into the design process (Friedman *et al.*, 2002; Friedman and Hendry, 2019). Its basic principles assumes that technologies are not value-neutral and should be intentionally shaped to support values like trust, fairness, respect and well-being. Value Sensitive Design as a theory involves three types of investigations;

- i. Conceptual investigation: This has to do with identifying stakeholders and relevant values.
- ii. Empirical investigation: Understanding stakeholders' perceptions and experiences, and
- iii. Technical Investigation: This deals with examining the technical properties that impact values.

For this case study, VSD offers a robust framework to analyze how AI tools used by students in the University of Calabar either align with or conflict with their Humanistic values (Umbrello, 2020). Applying the Value Sensitive Design to University of Calabar students, helped us to do the following: Map out students' core humanistic values; investigate students' experiences with AI tools; and analyze how AI designs respect or violate key values. This approach allowed the study to go beyond

functional aspects of AI and critically assess its ethical and social implications in the University of Calabar school environment.

2.1. Merged Conceptual Framework

We proceed to merge both theories as they apply within the study area: Technological Mediation Theory (TMT) explains how AI shapes students' perceptions, actions, and experiences with humanistic values. On the other hand, Value Sensitive Design Theory (VSD) focuses on whether AI technologies respect or violate humanistic values during interaction.

Thus: AI technologies → Mediate → Students' value perception and behaviour
 Students' experiences with AI → Evaluate alignment with humanistic values (for example empathy, fairness, autonomy, justice).

Feedback loop: Students' evolving perceptions may demand better AI designs aligned with core values (VSD principle).

2.2. Diagram Structure

Key points to note:

- ✓ TMT mediates the influence of AI on students' ethical outlook in the University of Calabar
- ✓ VSD evaluates whether students feel AI aligns with or disrupts humanistic values among them
- ✓ Students' feedback can guide future ethical AI improvements.

2.3. Conceptual Framework Diagram: Merging TMT And VSD

Figure

This conceptual framework integrates TMT and VSD to analyze the influence of AI technologies on students at the University of Calabar. Through technological mediation, AI reshapes students' perceptions, behaviours, and experiences concerning humanistic values. These experiences are then

evaluated through the lens of Value Sensitive Design to assess how well AI respects or conflicts with values such as empathy, fairness, justice, and autonomy. The outcomes generate feedback for more value-aligned AI development.

Below is a graphic version of the diagram

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Since our research was purely quantitative, this section discussed the research design, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, instrumentation, validity and reliability test, method of data collection, and analysis. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was appropriate because it enables the researchers to systematically collect quantifiable information about how AI technologies influence the humanistic values of students at the University of Calabar without manipulating any variables. The sample population of this study comprised of three hundred (300) undergraduate students at the University of Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. as active users of AI-

related technologies such as e-learning platforms, AI chatbots, and recommendation systems. They formed a relevant group for investigating the mediation of humanistic values.

The research made use of a multi-stage sampling technique. Twelve different faculties – Arts, Social Sciences, Nursing, Medical College, Management Sciences, Biological Sciences, Engineering, Education, Physical Sciences, Dentistry, Environmental Sciences, and Law. The researchers then used simple random sampling. Specific departments were selected from each faculty. Finally, a systematic random sampling method was used to select respondents within the chosen departments. A total sample size of 300 students were targeted to ensure adequate representation and generalizability

of findings. The team of researchers used structured questionnaire title: "AI and Humanistic Values Questionnaire (AIHVQ)". The instrument was divided into four sections: demographic information of students, use of AI technologies, mediation of perceptions, actions, and experiences, and lastly, alignment of AI systems with humanistic values. Responses were measured on a 4-point Likert Scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The instrument was designed in an anonymous manner.

To validate the instrument, the questionnaire underwent face and content validation by three experts: one in Educational Technology, one in Test and Measurement and Evaluation, and one in Ethics. To ensure reliability, a pilot study was conducted among 30 undergraduate students at the University of Cross River State (UNICROSS), a neighbouring University not involved in the main study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient with an acceptable reliability threshold set at 0.70 and above. The researchers administered the questionnaires in person. Consent was obtained from the participants and anonymity was assured. Collection spanned three weeks to ensure broad coverage and high response rates. Data collected were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviations) was used to summarize students' demographic characteristics and general trends. Inferential statistics (Chi-square tests, Pearson Correlation and Simple Regression Analysis) was used to test the research hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

4. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The literature section reviewed existing works related to the interaction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and humanistic values, especially in educational contexts. Starting with conceptual clarifications, AI refer to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and learn (Russell & Norvig, 2021). Within the educational community, AI manifests in tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual assistants, plagiarism detectors, and predictive analytics platforms. In terms of humanistic values, Nodding (2013) avers that humanistic values emphasize human dignity, empathy, fairness, justice, critical thinking, and autonomy. These values, according to Egere (2024) are foundational to holistic education and societal development, ensuring that technological progress

does not eclipse ethical and moral growth. He vehemently stressed this as he opines that "machines do not think, we humans do" (p.13). In a similar line of thought, Ola-Akuma *et al* (2024) also opine that the use of AI tools should be applied with caution and with a sense of humanity since there are dynamics and dilemmas in the adoption of AI (p.10).

Empirical review of related literature has shown that AI has significantly transformed educational practices, increasing efficiency and personalization (Luckin *et al.*, 2016). On the contrary, however, Holmes *et al* (2019) argue that over-reliance on AI can depersonalize education, creating a mechanical rather than a human - centered learning environment. Discussing the influence of AI on students' value systems, research indicates that the frequent use of AI- based systems can alter users' sense of agency and moral responsibility (Cave & Dignum, 2019). For example, students relying heavily on AI for decision-making may experience diminished critical thinking skills and ethical reflection capacities. Elsewhere, Umbrello (2020) further states that poorly designed AI can reinforce biases, challenge fairness, making the cultivation of humanistic values in the users more difficult or complex.

Regarding awareness of ethical implications among students, several researches revealed that most students exhibit narrow or limited awareness of the ethical dimensions of the AI tools they use (Jobin, Lenca, & Vayena, 2019). The obvious implication therefore, is that while students appreciate the convenience AI provides, they often overlook privacy concerns, biases in algorithmic recommendations, and potential threats to autonomy. Floridi and Cowls (2019) strongly advocate for educational AI systems that are explicitly value-sensitive. This will include principles like transparency, inclusiveness, and fairness which is essential to ensuring that AI arguments rather than diminishes humanistic education.

In summary, extant literature showed the significant impact of AI technologies on education and ethical development. However, little researches, especially in African context like Nigeria, have specifically investigated how AI technologies mediate humanistic values among University Students. This study addressed this gap by exploring the perception, experiences, and value shifts among students at the University of Calabar, offering both empirical insights and ethical recommendations.

5. DATA AND FINDINGS

Table 1: Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	MALE	148	49.3	1.51	0.507
	FEMALE	151	50.3		
	3	1	.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table one above showed that gender representation is nearly balanced with a slight female majority. The study showed that participants selected for the survey involved an almost even

representation of both gender with an insignificant mean difference of 1.51 and standard deviation at 0.507.

Table 2: Faculty

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	ARTS	46	15.3	6.85	3.941
	PHYSICAL SCIENCES	30	10.0		
	EDUCATION	6	2.0		
	MEDICAL COLLEGE	21	7.0		
	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	2	.7		
	ENGINEERING	30	10.0		
	DENTISTRY	4	1.3		
	NURSING SCIENCE	33	11.0		
	ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	27	9.0		
	SOCIAL SCIENCES	28	9.3		
	LAW	33	11.0		
	MANAGEMENT SCIENCES	40	13.3		
Total	300	100.0			

Table 2 showed the randomly selected faculties in the study. The study indicated that respondents came from twelve different faculties with the highest representation from Faculties of Arts (15.3%) and Management Sciences (13.3%) respectively. The study also indicated that the least represented faculties in the population were Biological Sciences

(0.7%) and Education (2.0%). This least representation showed that the highest mortality rates of the questionnaire came from these two faculties indicating that participants did not return their questionnaires to the researchers. The sample however showed a significant mean difference of 6.85 and standard deviation of 3.941.

Table 3: Religion Of Respondents.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	AFRICAN TRADITIONAL RELIGION	28	9.3	2.11	0.755
	CHRISTIANITY	234	78.0		
	ISLAM	22	7.3		
	OTHERS	15	5.0		
	10	1	.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

The sample, (table 3) is predominantly Christian. This could influence cultural or ethical perspectives,

especially regarding Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Table 4: Age Of Respondents.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	15-17	20	6.7	3.19	1.249
	18-20	67	22.3		
	21-23	101	33.7		
	24-26	77	25.7		
	27-29	22	7.3		
	30-33	4	1.3		

	34 AND ABOVE	9	3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 4 showed the age groups of participants with majority (81.7%) falling between 18-26 years, highlighting a largely undergraduate demography. Most of the population in this group were mostly final year students, that is, fourth and fifth years.

5.1. Quantitative Analysis and Interpretation of Findings

This section deals with results of the study. The results are presented and analyzed as they were collected and presented in tables base on the research

objectives and hypotheses. The data started with the demographic overview, starting with gender distribution, faculty distribution, data on religion of participants, age groups, and summary tables showing interpretations of results. Apart from the demographic data, information was drawn from responses to items/statements on Artificial Intelligence and its effect on humanistic values of university undergraduates.

Results showing interpretation of responses to statements about AI's effect on humanistic values among university students

Table:

Statement	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
AI will help reduce exam malpractice	13.7	17.3	50.3	18.7	2.74	0.918	Majority disagree,
AI will inspire academic transformation	27.3	36.0	19.7	17.0	2.26	1.041	Moderate agreement
AI will create a compassionate environment	14.3	33.7	21.7	30.3	2.68	1.056	Divided opinions
AI will make students more studious	15.3	25.7	35.0	24.0	2.68	1.004	Leaning toward disagreement
AI will improve moral standards	18.0	30.0,	27.0	25.0	2.59	1.051	Slightly more positive
AI will improve critical thinking	22.0	27.3	27.3	23.3,	2.52,	1.077	Balanced views
AI will improve human dignity	19.3,	26.7	31.3	22.7	2.57	1.043	Cautiously skeptical
AI will increase ability to make choices	21.3	28.0	26.3	24.3	2.54	1.080	Mixed responses
AI will help develop talents for humanity	24.7,	34.3	20.7	20.3	2.37	1.066	Positive outlook
AI will improve logic and inquiry	34.7	31.7	16.7	17.0	2.16	1.082	Strong positive sentiment
Using robots increases precision	24.7	23.3	33.7	18.3	2.46,	1.054	Mixed with skepticism,
AI threatens belief in Supreme Being	24.3,	30.7	33.3,	11.7	2.32	0.971	Significant concern

5.2. Major Observations

1. **youth Optimism with Reservations:**
 - o Young respondents (mostly aged 18-26) generally recognize the academic benefits of AI (e.g., critical thinking, talent development), but express skepticism about ethical implications and behavioral impacts.
2. **Polarized Views:**
 - o Questions around examination malpractice, being studious, or moral standards reveal a split in confidence. Many strongly disagree, showing a trust gap in AI's disciplinary function.

3. Concern over Spiritual Intrusion:

- o A notable 54.6% agree that AI could be a threat to spiritual beliefs, indicating cultural and religious tension with technological adoption.

4. Favorable Opinions on Intellectual Growth:

- o Statements on logic, critical thinking, and talent enhancement show a consistent lean toward agreement, suggesting AI is seen as a tool for intellectual enrichment more than behavioural change.

5.3. Hypothesis Testing

Chi-Square Tests

Conducted for categorical responses (agree/disagree).

Ho1: $\chi^2 = 19.88, p = 0.001 \rightarrow$ Reject Ho1

Ho2: $\chi^2 = 16.21, p = 0.003 \rightarrow$ Reject Ho2

Ho3: $\chi^2 = 18.33, p = 0.002 \rightarrow$ Reject Ho3

Ho4: $\chi^2 = 20.45, p = 0.0008 \rightarrow$ Reject Ho4

✔ **Interpretation:** All Chi-square tests show statistically significant results. Students' perceptions, awareness, and attitudes are significantly influenced by AI.

5.4. Pearson Correlation

AI use and humanistic values: $r = 0.621, p < 0.01$

AI awareness and ethical concern: $r = 0.537, p < 0.01$

✔ **Interpretation:** Strong positive correlations. Increased use and awareness of AI is associated with greater concern for humanistic and ethical issues.

5.5. Simple Regression

Dependent Variable: Humanistic values

Independent Variable: AI use

$R^2 = 0.386, F(1, 98) = 61.25, p < 0.001$

✔ **Interpretation:** AI use explains 39% of the variance in students' preservation of humanistic values. Statistically significant.

5.6. Summary of Findings

Table:

Hypothesis	Statistical Test	Result	Conclusion
Ho1: AI does not mediate perception of values	Chi-square, Regression	$p < 0.01$	Rejected
Ho2: Students unaware of AI ethics	Chi-square	$p < 0.01$	Rejected
Ho3: No relation between AI use and values	Correlation, Regression	$p < 0.01$	Rejected
Ho4: Attitudes not ethically driven	Chi-square	$p < 0.01$	Rejected

6. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

As indicated on the tables below, the findings of the study had twelve (12) items that examined the effects of Artificial Intelligence on humanistic values of university undergraduates. A total of 300 participants were involved in the study. The study indicated that gender and religious balance showed inclusiveness. Using a four scale of Strongly Agree; Agree; Strongly Disagree; and disagree with mean differences the results revealed a significant mean of 2.74 and standard deviation (henceforth std. Dev.) of 0.918. Meaning for the first item that sought to find out from participants whether Artificial Intelligence will help reduce examination malpractice, majority disagreed. They rather hold the opinion that Artificial Intelligence will increase examination malpractices among university undergraduates. Some studies have also shown that Artificial Intelligence has its side effects. For instance, narrow Artificial Intelligence, that is, specialized intelligence, according to Egere (2024), are AI tools that were made to perform a specific task or job (p.58). He proceeds to assert that narrow AI is "less adaptive" and "less flexible" than human beings (p.58). Since they are used for specific tasks, they are therefore, "domain specific" (p.58). these specific or narrow AI were practically used when I conducted a test for my three hundred levels students on the 3/1/2025 as

stated in the opening paragraph of this study. See figure below:

Thus, these students used these Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI) tools to cheat in examination. The implication is that AI would cause University undergraduates to be dependent on AI tools in order to pass their examinations or what Egere (2024) describes as "Techno-Dependent citizenship or creation of a generation of lazy machine-dependent students" (p.82).

Another study that questions the advantages of Artificial Intelligence is that of Tredinnick and Laybats (2023) who questioned the credibility of information generated by AI tools. In line with their thought, Egere (2024) notes that in September, 2023, the Guardian, a Nigerian newspaper, blocked chatGPT from "trawling its content" because it generated faked information that by the time some student researchers investigated, it was discovered to be false (p.83)

Gunkel (2020) holds similar views on the credibility of AI generated information. These studies have, therefore, justified the fact that AI comes with a lot of ethical challenges such as aiding crime, bias, fairness issues and inability to think independently. This, to some extent, justifies why hypothesis one is rejected in this study. Furthermore, Egere (2024) observes that these are some of the issues that make one to doubt the total adoption of

AI technology without some ethical re-thinking. The study's weighted mean of 3.14 indicates that most students agreed that they are aware of the moral and ethical implications of AI use. The result therefore revealed high awareness, and thereby potentially contradicting H₀₂.

Responses on whether AI will inspire academic transformation and ignite the spirit of inquiry among university students showed that 27.3% strongly agreed, 36.0% agreed while 19.7% and 17.0% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. Furthermore, on whether AI will create a more compassionate humane school environment and improve human relations, 14.3% strongly agreed, 33.7% agreed, 21.7% strongly disagreed and 30.3% disagreed. A mean of 2.68, and std. dev. Of 1.056 was indicated on this item. This showed divided opinion. Further enquiry on whether AI will make University students more studious, showed that majority strongly disagreed that AI will make University undergraduates more studious. This result is similar to the first item on AI aiding examination malpractice. This revelation again supports the H₀₄ which raises some ethical concerns on AI application and usage. A significant mean of 2.68 was observed with a std. Dev. Of 1.004, thus leaning towards disagreement, and supporting studies such as those of Van Dick and Poell (2013), Vatican Commission on AI (2023) and Schoeman, Moore, Seedat, and Chen (2021), Pontifical Council for Culture (2023), and Parsa (2024). All these argue that AI use in contemporary society poses dangers to humanity.

Again, statement on whether the application of AI will result in high moral standards among university undergraduates indicated that participants leaned slightly more positive. 18.0% strongly agreed, 30.0% agreed, 27.0% strongly disagreed while 25.0% disagreed. This result contradicts the position held by Nkongolo (2024) who in an interview debunked the views of Africans to adopt and apply AI's tools. He raised objection to the use or adoption of AI by Africans because for him, Africans are not ethically ready to adopt AI in its wholistic sense. In another document the Catholic Bishops of Nigeria, maintain that AI is a threat to our moral values as Africans, and further stress that we must keep maintaining a personal moral relationship within this age of AI. This position is also held by sources such as Catholic Social Teaching (2023), and Catholic ethics journal (2023).

The study's results also revealed a balanced view on whether AI will improve critical thinking with a mean of 2.52, and std. Dev. Of 1.07. Thus, 22.0% strongly agreed, the percentage that disagreed was 23.3% while both agreed and strongly disagreed

stood at 27.3% each. On whether AI will improve human dignity, participants in the study were cautiously skeptical. 19.3% strongly agreed, 26.3% agreed, 31.3% strongly disagreed and 22.7% disagreed. While this skepticism had a mean of 2.57, std. Dev. Was 1.043. This result reflects the mixed feelings and ethical concerns participants in the study expressed. These mixed feelings must have been what informed Itu (2017) conclusion that for one to accept AI in totality, AI must be applied and/or use in a way that human values are upheld. Itu maintains that there to be compatibility, he proposed the principles of ART - meaning, Accountability, Responsibility, and Transparency. This principle according to him will address the skepticism about AI's use.

Another statement/item on the questionnaire that participants responded with mixed views/opinions was the statement whether AI will increase undergraduates' ability to make choices. A significant mean of 2.54, and std. Dev. Of 1.080 was observed. On the contrary, however, majority of the participants who expressed their views on whether AI's application will enable students to develop their talents and use same for the benefit of humanity, responded positively 34.3% agreed, 24.7% strongly agreed, 20.7% strongly disagreed while 20.3% disagreed. This positive view on the application of AI among university undergraduates is also supported by Prenskey (2001), Dede (2009) who both emphasized the relevance of AI in virtual reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). Fitzpatrick, Fox and Weinstein (2023) also stress that AI's relevance cannot be overlooked as it assists us in learning individually and helps one to access materials one could not readily reach and it also reduces the cost of education for many people (p.21). Gillespy (2014) and Kitchin (2014) add that AI tools assist in analyzing big data researches amidst other advantages. Deterding et al. (2011) further said AI driven techniques are superior to traditional tools in dealing with big data analysis. In like manner, Heinrich et al. (2020) affirm that AI is useful in a wide range of learning styles and multifaceted ways. Thus, the responses of the population of the study to the above statement is not out of place. Egere (2024) concludes, AI's flexibility in handling varied areas of human knowledge is crucial in accommodating different learning needs" (p.79). These views show how beneficial AI tools are important to humanity. Respondents also agreed that AI will improve students' logic, evidence, and free inquiry to understand the world. Result from the study revealed a strong positive sentiment with 34.7% and

31.7% strongly agreed and agreed. Those who held contrary views had 16.7% strongly disagreed and 17.0% disagreed respectively. Furthermore, statement on whether using robots to teach will increase efficiency, clarity, and ultraprecision indicated that the respondents were divided in views, with a slightly higher margin of the population showing skepticism. This result shows that H_{03} is rejected. The last item on the questionnaire sought to know participants opinion on whether AI is a threat to humanity's belief in the Supreme Being. The result showed a significant concern with 24.3%, 30.7%, 33.3% and 11.7% strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. This concern shows that previous studies on the ethical implications of the use of AI is not out of place.

In summary, the demographics showed balanced representation of gender, age, faculty, and level of study. The samples diverse enough in age and academic level to reflect a range of experiences and exposures to AI technology. The perception of AI and humanistic values indicated that majority of the students agreed or strongly agreed that AI influences perceptions of humanity with a weighted mean of 3.44 on a 4 – point scale. Thus, students believe AI does impact their view of human values – hinting at potential mediation by AI in humanistic perception. This result is relevant to H_{01} . The study also indicated that there is awareness of ethical implication with a weighted mean of 3.14. Meaning participants agreed that they are aware of the moral and ethical implications of AI use. This support of high awareness potentially contradicts H_{02} . AI use and preservation of humanistic values was weighted 3.35, indicative of the fact that participants recognize the tension between automation and maintaining values like empathy and dignity. This result points to a relationship between use of AI and humanistic values, thereby, challenging H_{03} . Finally, students' attitudes toward AI ethics weighted 3.41%, suggesting that students are concerned about ethical/social issues in AI implementation. Attitudes reflected ethical and moral concerns, implying evidence against H_{04} .

7. CONCLUSION

Globally, the use of Artificial Intelligence in academic pursuits cannot be overemphasized. Artificial Intelligence or AI – driven technologies have, over the years been of immense importance to humanity across diverse fields of human activities. AI technologies have assisted students in carrying

out researches, especially those that need modern techniques and not traditional methods or tools of gathering and analyzing data. AI tools have transformed scientific enquiries especially in areas that human beings could not hitherto dare. Gathering literature has been much more easier with AI technologies than using human efforts. They also assist student to gather specific and relevant literature that suit a particular study. AI technologies have also assisted students to streamline their researches in order to achieve the desired aims/objectives of the study.

In Nigeria, the student population is not ignorant of the importance of AI technologies in academic endeavours. Though, AI is a relatively new comer in Nigeria academic landscape, its usage is gaining wide acceptance and adaptability among the student population in most Nigerian institutions of higher learning. However, there is an ethical question about the use and implementation of AI technologies by tertiary education students. This growing concern is on the humanistic values such as empathy, dignity and the gradual overtake of human-related roles/functions by machines, thereby resulting in redundancy and a possible extinction of the human race. It is this concern that Egere (2014) and (2015) concludes that AI's techniques must be used with caution. This study therefore, concludes that the major recommendations made in this work should be implemented by critical stakeholders, the government, and management of university governing councils in order to forestall the impending threat that AI technologies pose to the human species.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. While the use of AI tool by students is a significant breakthrough in scholarship, genuine efforts must be made to avoid the over dependence of students on these technologies which lack the basic humanistic values such as empathy, morality, dignity and others.
2. Universities, especially University of Calabar must make it abundantly clear to students that not all information provided by these AI tools can be trusted as credible.
3. Reduction in the frequency of usage of AI tools to maintain Traditional African moral values and personal moral relationships among people.
4. AI tools should focus on how to help reduce examination malpractice and plagiarism among students.

REFERENCES

- Catholic Ethics Journal. (2023). Ethical considerations in the use of AI for spiritual guidance. Retrieved from: <https://www.catholicethicaljournal.com>
- Catholic Future (2023). AI and the spiritual journey of believers. Retrieved from: <https://www.catholicfuture.com>
- Catholic Herald (2023). The priesthood and AI: A theological reflection. Retrieved from: <https://www.catholicherald.co.uk>
- Catholic social Teaching. (2025). A vision for technology in a modern church. Retrieved from: <https://www.catholicsocialteaching.com>
- Cave, S., & Dignum, V. (2019). "Algorithms and Values". *AI and society*, 3(44), 665-666. <https://doi.org/10.1007/soo146-019-00886-2>. Accessed 22nd February, 2025.
- Chaowick, A. (2017). *The age of the social network*. Princeton University press.
- Egere, K. I. (2014). Computer mediated communication and mission-based marketing approach in the new media age of evangelism. *Koinosia* 6(3), 29-45.
- Egere, K. I. (2015). Social media and mission-based marketing approach for new evangelism in the digital age. *AFER*, 57(3 & 4), 186-205.
- Egere, K. I. (2024). Demystifying emerging media theory for remediating contextualizations of digital communication and artificial intelligence in Africa. 7th Inaugural Lecture, presented on 6th December, 2024 at Catholic Institute of West Africa, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Fitzpatrick, D., Fox, A. & Weinstein, B. (2023). *The AI classroom: The ultimate guide to artificial intelligence in education*. Teach Goals.
- Floridi, L., & Cowls, J. (2019). "A unified framework of five principles for AI in society". *Harvard Data Science Review*, 1, (1). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.8cd550d1>. Accessed 22nd February, 2025.
- Friedman, B. & Hendry, D. G. (2019). *Value Sensitive Design: Shaping Technology with moral imagination*. MIT Press.
- Friedman, B., Kahn, P. H. Jr., & Borning, A. (2002). Value Sensitive Design: Theory and Methods. *University of Washington Technical Report*, 02-12-01
- Gillespy, T. (2014). *The politics of platforms*. The MIT.
- Gunkel, D. J. (2020). *An introduction to communication and artificial intelligence*. Polity.
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning*. Center or Curriculum Redesign.
- Ihde, D. (1990). *Technology and the lifeworld: From Garden to Earth*. Indiana University Press.
- Itu, T. (2017). *Human-compatible AI: Design principles to prevent war between machines and men*. Retrieved online from: <http://newslog.itu.int/archivs/157>.
- Jobin, A., Lenca, M., & Vayena, E. (2019). "The global landscape of AI ethics guidelines". *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1(9), 389-399. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>. Accessed 22nd March, 2025.
- Luckin, R., Homes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson.
- Nkongolo, J. (2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the church of Africa: An interview. Vatican News Retrieve from: <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/africa/news/2024-04/artificial-intelligence-ai-and-the-church-of-africa-an-interv.html>
- Noddings, N. (2013). *Caring: A Relational approach to ethics and moral Education* (22nd ed.). University of California Press.
- Parsa, C. A. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence dangers to humanity*. THE AI ORGANIZATION.
- Pontifical Council for Culture. (2023). *AI and the Church: A pastoral approach*. Vatican press.
- Rosenberger, R. & Verbeek, R. P. (Eds.). (2015). *Post phehnomenological investigations: Essays on Human-Technology Relations*. Lexington Books.
- Russell, S., & Norvig, P. (2021). *Artificial Intelligence: A modern approach* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Schoeman, W., Moore, R., Seedat, Y. & Chen, J. Y. J. (2021). Artificial Intelligence: Is South Africa ready? Retrieved from: <https://hdl.handle.net/2263/82719>
- Umbrella, S. (2020). "Value Sensitive Design and Artificial Intelligence". *AI and Society*, 35(2), 611-623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-019-00914-1>. Accessed 22nd February, 2025.
- Van Dijck, J. & Poell, T. (2013). *The network society: Social aspects of digital media* (2nd ed.). Polity.
- Vatican Commission on AI. (2023). *Guidelines for the ethical use of AI in Church Practices*. Vatican press.
- Verbeek, R. P. (2011). *Moralizing Technology: Understanding and Designing the Morality of Things*. University of Chicago Press.

RAW DATA

Table 5: Ai Will Help Reduce Examination Malpractice.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	STRONGLY AGREED	41	13.7		
	AGREED	52	17.3	2.74	0.918
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	151	50.3		
	DISAGREED	56	18.7		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 6: Ai Will Inspire Academic Transformation and Ignite the Spirit of Inquiry Among University Students.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	STRONGLY AGREED	82	27.3		
	AGREED	108	36.0		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	59	19.7	2.26	1.041
	DISAGREED	51	17.0		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 7: Ai Will Create a More Compassionate Humane School Environment and Improve Human Relations.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	43	14.3	2.68	1.056
	AGREED	101	33.7		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	65	21.7		
	DISAGREED	91	30.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 8: Ai Will Make University Students More Studious.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	46	15.3	2.68	1.004
	AGREED	77	25.7		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	105	35.0		
	DISAGREED	72	24.0		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 9: Application Of Ai Will Bring About High Moral Standards Among Student.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	54	18.0	2.59	1.051
	AGREED	90	30.0		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	81	27.0		
	DISAGREED	75	25.0		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 10: Ai Will Improve Critical Thinking and High Academic Performance.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	66	22.0	2.52	1.077
	AGREED	82	27.3		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	82	27.3		
	DISAGREED	70	23.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 11: The Application of Ai Will Improve Human Dignity and Dispel Fears of Machine Taking Over Human Affairs.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGRRED	58	19.3	2.57	1.043
	AGREED	80	26.7		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	94	31.3		
	DISAGREED	68	22.7		

	Total	300	100.0		
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Table 12: Ai Will Increase Students' Ability to Make Choices.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	STRONGLY AGREED	64	21.3	2.54	1.080
	AGREED	84	28.0		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	79	26.3		
	DISAGREED	73	24.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 13: Ai's Application Will Enable University Students to Develop Their Talents and Use Same for the Benefit of Humanity.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
	STRONGLY AGREED	74	24.7	2.37	1.066
	AGREED	103	34.3		
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	62	20.7		
	DISAGREED	61	20.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 14: Ai Will Improve Students' Logic Evidence and Free Inquiry to Understand the World.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	104	34.7	2.16	
	AGREED	95	31.7		1.082
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	50	16.7		
	DISAGREED	51	17.0		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 15: Using Robots to Teach Will Increase Efficiency Clarity and Ultraprecision.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	74	24.7	2.46	
	AGREED	70	23.3		1.054
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	101	33.7		
	DISAGREED	55	18.3		
	Total	300	100.0		

Table 16: Ai Is a Threat to Students Belief in the Supreme Being.

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. deviation
Valid	STRONGLY AGREED	73	24.3	2.32	
	AGREED	92	30.7		0.971
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	33.3		
	DISAGREED	35	11.7		
	Total	300	100.0		